

Synthesis of (+)-17,18-Dimethoxyhexahydrohimbane A Key Intermediate in the Synthesis of Deserpidine Analogue

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An interesting method has been developed for the synthesis of (±)-17,18-dimethoxyhexahydrohimbane (12)—a key intermediate in the synthesis of deserpidine analogue. 6,7-Dimethoxy-3-isochromanone (10) was used as the desired synthon for generating the non-nitrogenous moiety. The latter on condensation with tryptamine followed by a series of reactions yielded (±)-17,18-dimethoxyhexahydrohimbane.

IN continuation of our earlier work¹ on the synthesis of yohimbinoïd alkaloids we have developed an interesting method for (±)-17,18-dimethoxyhexahydrohimbane (12) which is a key intermediate for entry into the deserpidine system (13).

6,7-Dimethoxy-3-isochromanone (10) has been used as synthon for the construction of the non-nitrogenous portion. It was obtained from 5,6-dimethoxy-2-indanone (9) by Baeyer-Villiger oxidation (Chart 1). The indanone derivative (9) was synthesised via an interesting diazoketone cyclisation procedure. When 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl diazomethyl ketone (8) was allowed to react with trifluoroacetic acid at -20° the indanone derivative (9) was obtained in 70% yield along with two minor products 9b and 9c, the latter being a spiro compound. The diazomethyl ketone (8) was prepared from 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl acetyl chloride (7) and ethereal diazomethane². 3,4-Dimethoxyphenylacetic acid (6) required for the synthesis was prepared from vanillin (1) (Chart 1). Vanillin on methylation afforded 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (2), which was converted to the 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl alcohol (3) by cross-Cannizzaro reaction. The bromide (4) prepared from 3 on treatment with sodium cyanide afforded the cyano derivative (5). The latter was subsequently hydrolysed with sodium hydroxide. Subsequent acidification of the reaction mixture afforded 3,4-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid (6) in good yield (75%).

The cyclisation of the 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl diazomethyl ketone proved interesting. The isolation of the spiro compound (9c) suggested the intermediacy of an oxonium salt through the 1,4-participation of the diazoketone moiety with the aryl nucleus involving the methoxy at C₄ (Chart 2). The formation of the indanone derivatives 9a and 9b could be explained by migration of one of the spiro bonds attached to C₁ either to C₆ or to C₂. The formation of 9a and 9b could also be possible by the direct participation of the methoxyl at C₈ on the

Chart 1

diazoketone unit causing an intramolecular Friedel-Craft type alkylation. The poor yield of the 2-indanone derivative (9b) was possibly due to steric hindrance caused by the methoxyl at C₈.

Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of 5,6-dimethoxy-2-indanone (9) with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid afforded

the key synthon, 6,7-dimethoxy-3-isochromanone (10). The structure of the lactone (10) was confirmed from its spectral data. For the synthesis of the deserpidine and its analogue (13), the substituted-hydroxyamide (11) was first generated by condensing tryptamine with the lactone (10; yield 75%) in refluxing ethanol under a nitrogen atmosphere; m/z 368 (M^+), 350 ($M^+ - H_2O$); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 440 (OH), 3 360 (NH) and 1 630 cm^{-1} (C=O); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 290, 283, 222 and 211 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.97, 3.98, 4.65 and 4.66 respectively); ^1H nmr (80 MHz) δ (d_6 -DMSO) 2.69–3.10 (4H, m, $\text{NH-CH}_2\text{CH}_2$), 3.35 (2H, s, ArCH_2CO), 3.66 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.70 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.42 (2H, d, J 5.0 Hz, collapses to a singlet on shaking with D_2O , $\text{CH}_2\text{-OH}$), 5.13 (1H, t, J 5.0 Hz, exchangeable with D_2O , CH_2OH), 6.77–7.51 (7H, m, Ar), 8.30 (1H, t, J 5.0 Hz, exchangeable with D_2O , CONHCH_2) and 10.69 (1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , indole NH).

(±)-17,18-Dimethoxyhexadehydrohimbane (12) was synthesised from the hydroxyamide (11) by Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation with phosphorous oxychloride followed by reduction with sodium borohydride. The cyclisation with phosphorous oxychloride failed using benzene and acetonitrile as solvent at various temperatures. It was achieved by refluxing the hydroxyamide (11) with only phosphorous oxychloride under a nitrogen atmosphere⁵. The double cyclisation of 11 with the formation of C and D rings occurred possibly via the imide intermediate; the latter was not isolated. The reaction product was directly reduced with sodium borohydride. The spectrum of 12 showed ν_{\max} 3 340 cm^{-1} (indole NH); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 290, 283, 225 and 211 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.99, 4.04, 5.58 and 4.52 respectively); m/z 334 (M^+), 333, 169 and 164 (100%) which indicated the presence of a hexadehydrohimbane system: ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 2.63–

3.29 (6H, m, $\text{C}_5\text{-H}_2$, $\text{C}_6\text{-H}_2$ and $\text{C}_{14}\text{-H}_2$), 3.79–4.09 (8H, br s, $\text{C}_{17}\text{-OCH}_3$, $\text{C}_{18}\text{-OCH}_3$ and $\text{C}_{21}\text{-H}_2$), 4.14 (1H, ill-resolved, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 6.59 (1H, s, $\text{C}_{16}\text{-H}$ or $\text{C}_{19}\text{-H}$), 6.64 (1H, s, $\text{C}_{18}\text{-H}$ or $\text{C}_{16}\text{-H}$), 7.07–7.51 (4H, m, Ar), 7.87 (1H, s, NH, exchangeable with D_2O). The structure of 12 was further confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample⁴.

Experimental

The melting points were recorded in a metal block and are uncorrected. The uv spectra were measured in 95% aldehyde free ethanol with a Varian 634 spectrophotometer, the ir spectra with Beckmann IR 20 and Perkin-Elmer IR 782 spectrophotometers and ^1H nmr spectra with a Varian CFT-20 (80 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction having boiling range 60–80°. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used to dry the organic solvents.

3,4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde: A solution of sodium hydroxide (35 ml; 20% strength) at 100° was added to vanillin (15.2 g, 100 mmol) in water (40 ml) on a steam-bath. While the heating was continued dimethyl sulphate (15.8 g; 14.2 ml; 125 mmol) was added to it, just rapidly enough to maintain a gentle ebullition. The reaction mixture was further heated (30 min) and an additional portion of dimethyl sulphate (3.0 g, 2.7 ml) was added till the reaction mixture showed acidic behaviour towards litmus. After heating the reaction mixture for another 10 min, it was rendered alkaline by adding sodium hydroxide solution (6 ml; 2% by strength) followed by the addition of dimethyl sulphate (3.0 g, 2.7 ml). This alternate addition of sodium hydroxide solution and of dimethyl sulphate was repeated twice. The reaction mixture was subsequently made strongly alkaline, heated for 20 min and rapidly cooled to 25° with continuous stirring. 3,4-Demethoxybenzaldehyde was extracted with ether (4 × 100 ml). The combined ether extracts were washed and dried. On removal of the solvent the oily residue solidified at 6° (14 g, 84%), m.p. 45° (lit.⁶ 46°) (Found: C, 65.24; H, 6.21. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 65.06; H, 6.01%).

3,4-Dimethoxybenzyl alcohol (3): A mixture of 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (13.6 g, 82 mmol) in methanol (20 ml) and 37–40% formalin (8 ml) was heated to 65°. The reaction flask was sprayed with cold water while a solution of potassium hydroxide (13.8 g, 246 mmol) in water (10 ml) was added rapidly to it maintaining the internal temperature at 65–75°. The reaction mixture was further heated at 70° for 40 min and then refluxed for another 20 min. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with methylene chloride (3 × 100 ml). The combined methylene chloride extracts were washed with water (4 × 50 ml) and dried. 3,4-Dimethoxybenzyl alcohol was distilled over at 162–65°/6 mm (8.5 g, 61.7%)

(Found: C, 64.47; H, 7.33. $C_9H_{11}O_2$ calcd. for: C, 64.28; H, 7.13%).

3,4-Dimethoxybenzyl bromide (4): To 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl alcohol (8.0 g, 47.6 mmol) dry carbon tetrachloride (20 ml) and dry triethylamine (4 ml) were added at 0°. Phosphorous tribromide (4 ml) was subsequently added dropwise to keep the reaction under control. After complete addition the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. The reaction mixture was then poured onto crushed ice and allowed to stand at room temperature for 1.5 h. It was extracted with methylene chloride, washed with water to remove the adhering acid and dried. On removal of methylene chloride a yellow oil was obtained which was distilled fractionally under reduced pressure to get 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl bromide, b.p. 140°/0.8–1 mm (8.8 g, 80%) (Found: C, 46.65; H, 4.97. $C_9H_{11}O_2Br$ calcd. for: C, 46.76; H, 4.76%).

3,4-Dimethoxybenzyl cyanide (5): To a solution of 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl bromide (8.5 g, 37 mmol) in ethanol (40 ml) was added dropwise a solution of sodium cyanide (9.1 g, 185 mmol) dissolved in aqueous ethanol. The temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at 55–60°. The mixture was subsequently refluxed for 5 h. The precipitated sodium bromide was filtered off and washed with little ethanol. The residue obtained after removal of the solvent was poured into ice-cold water. The mixture was extracted with chloroform (3 × 75 ml) and the extract was washed with water and dried. On removal of the solvent 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl cyanide was obtained which was crystallised from chloroform–ether, m.p. 62–3° (lit.² 64–5°) (Found: C, 67.58; H, 6.41, N, 7.61. $C_{10}H_{11}NO_2$ calcd. for: C, 67.79; H, 6.21; N, 7.90%).

3,4-Dimethoxyphenylacetic acid (6): To a solution of 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl cyanide (4.5 g, 25 mmol) in methanol (30 ml) was added a solution of potassium hydroxide (2.0 g, 37 mmol) dissolved in water (8 ml). The mixture was refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere for 5 h, cooled and diluted with water. It was then extracted with ether (4 × 50 ml) to remove the unreacted cyanide. The aqueous portion was cooled and acidified with 6 N hydrochloric acid. The resulting white semi-solid mass was dissolved in ether (5 × 60 ml), washed with water (3 × 40 ml) and dried. On removal of the solvent 3,4-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid was obtained as a gummy solid which was crystallised from benzene–petrol, m.p. 85° (lit.² anhyd. 98–9°) (3.7 g, 74.2%) (Found: C, 61.35; H, 6.04. $C_{10}H_{12}O_4$ calcd. for: C, 61.22, H, 6.12%).

3,4-Dimethoxybenzyl diazomethyl ketone (8): To a solution of 3,4-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid (3.5 g, 17.8 mmol) in dry benzene (50 ml), oxalyl chloride (5 ml, 37.5 mmol) in dry benzene (25 ml) was added dropwise at room temperature. The mixture was stirred vigorously during addition and stirring was continued for further 1 h. The solvent and excess reagent were removed under reduced pressure. The oily acid chloride was dissolved in

benzene (20 ml) and added dropwise with stirring to an ice-cold solution of dry ethereal diazomethane (large excess). After 2 h the solvent was removed. The residue on chromatography over neutral alumina afforded 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl diazomethyl ketone, m.p. 60° (2.7 g, 68.7%) in the 50% petrol–ether eluent (Found: C, 60.21, H, 5.23, N, 12.43. $C_{11}H_{13}N_2O_2$ calcd. for: C, 60.00; H, 5.45, N, 12.73%).

Cyclisation of 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl diazomethyl ketone to 5,6-dimethoxy-2-indanone (9a): A solution of trifluoroacetic acid (25 ml) in dry methylene chloride (20 ml) was stirred at –20° under an atmosphere of nitrogen followed by slow addition of 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl diazomethyl ketone (2.6 g, 127.4 mmol) in dry methylene chloride (15 ml). The mixture was then stirred for 10 min. The solvent and excess trifluoroacetic acid were removed under reduced pressure. The residue on column chromatography over silica gel afforded the indanone (9) as a crystalline solid, m.p. 119°d (lit.⁵ 120°d) in the benzene eluent, (1.6 g, 70%) (Found: C, 68.98, H, 6.42. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2$ calcd. for: C, 68.75, H, 6.25%).

The residual gummy mass obtained in the eluate was subjected to preparative thin layer chromatography in benzene–ethyl acetate (2:1) mixture over silica gel. Two minor semi-solid products could be isolated. On subsequent purification compounds 9b and 9c were obtained: 9b (0.108 g, 5%); ν_{max} (neat) 1745 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (CDCl₃; 80 MHz) 3.42 (2H, s, OMe–2H), 3.57 (2H, s, C₈–2H), 3.77 (6H, s, OMe) and 6.51–6.71 (2H, m, C₆–H and C₇–H); 9c (0.117 g, 6%); ν_{max} (neat) 1785 (C–O) and 1660 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (CDCl₃; 80 MHz) 2.07 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 2.56 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 3.79 (3H, s, OMe), 6.57 (1H, s, MeO–C=CH), 6.69 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, O=C–CH=CH) and 7.30 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, C=CH).

6,7-Dimethoxy-3-isochromanone (10): To a well-cooled solution of 5,6-dimethoxy-2-indanone (9a; 1.5 g, 7.8 mmol) in dry methylene chloride (10 ml) a cooled solution of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (2.587 g, 15 mmol) in dry methylene chloride (70 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously at 0° for 1 h and then kept at 0° for 10 days. The excess peracid was decomposed with 2% aqueous sodium sulphite solution and the precipitated *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid was filtered off and washed with a little methylene chloride. The filtrate was washed with 2% sodium bicarbonate solution. After usual work up the residue from methylene chloride extract was chromatographed over silica gel. 6,7-Dimethoxy-3-isochromanone (10) was obtained from benzene–ethyl acetate (4:1) fraction, m.p. 105–06° (methanol) (lit.² 108–09.5°), (1.0 g, 61.5%) (Found: C, 63.18, H, 5.92. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ calcd. for: C, 63.46, H, 5.76%).

The hydroxyamide (11): A mixture of tryptamine (0.692 g, 4.3 mmol) and 6,7-dimethoxy-3-isochromanone (0.900 g, 4.3 mmol) was dissolved in

absolute ethanol (60 ml) and was refluxed under a nitrogen blanket for 20 h. The residue from the solvent was chromatographed over neutral alumina. The benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) eluate afforded the hydroxyamide (**11**), m.p. 180–82° (benzene-ethyl acetate) (1.2 g, 75.4%) (Found : C, 68.65, H, 6.87, N, 7.36. $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_4$ calcd. for : C, 68.46, H, 6.52, N, 7.60%).

(±)-17,18-Dimethoxyhexadehydroyohimbane (**12**) : Freshly distilled phosphorus oxychloride⁵ (80 ml) was added under a flow of nitrogen to the hydroxyamide (**11**; 0.736 g, 2.0 mmol). The solution was heated at 80° for 1.5 h with constant stirring. On removal of the excess phosphorus oxychloride a red gummy residue was obtained. It was dissolved in methanol-water (4 : 1; 30 ml) mixture. The solution was cooled in an ice-bath and to it sodium borohydride (2.0 g) was added in portions over a period of 1 h and then kept for 12 h at room temperature. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure. The excess borohydride was decomposed with ice-cold water and the reaction mixture was extracted with chloroform (4 × 75 ml), washed and dried. Removal of the solvent afforded a gummy residue which was chromatographed over a column of neutral alumina. The benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluate gave (±)-17,18-dimethoxyhexadehydro-

yohimbane, m.p. 246–48° (lit.⁴ 250–51°) (0.1 g, 14.97%) (Found : C, 75.62; H, 6.42; N, 8.48. $C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_2$ calcd. for : C, 75.44; H, 6.58; N, 8.38%).

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References

1. U. K. PANDIT, B. DAS and A. CHATTERJEE, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, 43, 4235
2. A. CHATTERJEE and S. GHOSH, *Syntheses*, 1981, 818
3. R. B. WOODWARD, F. F. BADER, H. BICKEL, A. J. FRY and KIERSTAD, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, 2, 1.
4. Provided by Professor U. K. PANDIT, Organic Laboratory, University of Amsterdam, Netherlands (Personal communication).
5. R. J. SPANGLER, B. G. BRCKMANN and J. H. KIM, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, 42, 2989.